

MODERN INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TO FOREIGN STUDENTS

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Abstract. This article discusses the importance of using modern information technologies in teaching Russian as a foreign language. Examples of using various information and communication technologies that can improve the learning process are given.

Keywords: information technologies, communication technologies in education, multimedia technologies, Russian as a foreign language (RFL).

In recent years, the need to change the forms of learning Russian as a foreign language has become increasingly evident. In recent years, it has become increasingly evident that the forms of studying Russian as a foreign language need to be changed. The classical lesson system is no longer in tune with the rapidly changing socio-cultural environment, which presents a demand for the active mastering of the language with a specific purpose and within the framework of a specific realized request. Traditional methods of teaching a foreign language, which presuppose the assimilation of knowledge in artificial situations, have ceased to meet the motivation of the students artificial situations, no longer meet the motivational needs of learners. This statement does not imply that the traditional teaching system has outlived its usefulness. On the contrary, information technologies allow to activate the practical side of language teaching more actively side of language teaching, as it allows the use of an unlimited number of different virtual situations, complementing the practical side of language teaching of different virtual situations, thus complementing the traditional teacher-student paradigm teacher-student paradigm. Today's students prefer to learn through active engagement rather than ready-made systems. But that doesn't mean that traditional classrooms lack engagement. In fact, information technology enhances engagement by creating a virtual, interactive space that is not limited by time or location. Rapidly changing social conditions and the increasing importance of information technology are also changing opportunities in education, allowing the use of computers, gadgets, cloud technology and other tools for learning. Therefore, it seems important to

create a new approach to education that combines traditional and innovative technologies in harmony.

The use of modern technologies in teaching Russian to foreign students is becoming an increasingly popular and effective method of learning. Nowadays, mobile applications, online resources and specialized educational programs provide new opportunities for mastering the Russian language. Examining these latest methods and approaches will allow readers to understand the advantages they offer, such as individualized approach and engaging forms of learning, as well as identify potential limitations, such as dependence on internet access or the need for teacher support.

Online courses and webinars play a key role in teaching Russian to international students. Interactive online courses provide an opportunity to learn Russian at a convenient time, receive feedback from teachers and interact with classmates from different countries. It is a convenient and accessible way of learning that allows you to customize the learning process to meet the individual needs of each student. For example, webinars can include hands-on lessons that include learning games and assignments that promote spelling, grammar, and pronunciation. Online courses may also offer access to authentic materials such as audio, video, and text resources that can help students immerse themselves in the language environment and improve their listening comprehension and reading skills. These online resources also often include opportunities to interact with native speakers, which helps students expand their vocabulary and practice speaking.

Mobile language learning applications play an important role in teaching Russian to foreign students. They provide a wide range of interactive exercises, dictionaries, audio and video lessons, which makes the learning process more fun and accessible. Thanks to these apps, students can learn Russian at any convenient time and place and improve their language skills using a variety of learning resources, including specialized apps for grammar, conversation practice and vocabulary development. Mobile apps for learning Russian can include such popular developments as Duolingo, Babbel, Rosetta Stone, Memrise and others. They provide a wide range of lessons and game exercises designed specifically for learning Russian, as well as offering the ability to listen to audio and video materials to practice listening comprehension and pronunciation. Such applications make learning Russian more interactive and accessible to users with different levels of proficiency.

Online games designed for learning help students to activate their language skills and inspire them to learn more effectively. Such games offer a variety of tasks to develop reading, writing, grammar, and listening comprehension skills. They also promote vocabulary development and speaking practice, providing students not only an interesting addition to the learning process, but also an opportunity to practice and improve their knowledge in an interactive and fun way.

Innovative approaches in the field of education have made it possible to develop adaptive educational programs that are individually customized for each student. They take into account the level of language proficiency as well as overall learning goals. In this way, students can receive a personalized learning plan that best suits their needs and abilities, which contributes to their more effective learning.

In conclusion, the use of modern technologies in teaching Russian to foreign students is an important tool that contributes to personalized and more effective learning. However, despite the advantages, it is necessary to take into account the potential limitations and disadvantages of such technologies. The implementation of modern educational methods and applications requires a balance between individualized approach and teacher support. It is important to consider both technological capabilities and pedagogical aspects in order to provide the best learning experience for students.

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